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The seventh international scientific
and professional conference

THE RIGHT TO ACCESS (MENTAL) HEALTH CARE

Conference Papers

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MENTAL HEALTH IN ADOLESCENCE: RELATIONS BETWEEN EMOTION REGULATION AND LIFE SATISFACTION

***Abstract:** Previous studies of mental health among youth have indicated that emotional processes are very important indicators of subjective well-being, especially in the period of adolescence. Considering that adolescents face developmental and accidental crises, coping with stress through adequate regulation of emotions is a significant factor for a mentally healthy life in this period. The aim of this research was to examine the relationship between emotion regulation and life satisfaction in adolescents. The sample of 155 adolescents from Serbia filled out the emotion regulation questionnaire (ERQ) and the life satisfaction scale (SWLS). The results indicate that a higher degree of emotion suppression, as well as a lower degree of cognitive reappraisal of a stressful event, significantly compromises life satisfaction in adolescents. The mentioned mechanisms were discussed in the paper, and the need for greater access of young people to institutions for the protection of mental health was pointed out.*

***Keywords:** adolescence, emotion regulation, life satisfaction, mental health.*

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1. Introduction

According to WHO³, up to 50% of all mental health conditions start before the age of 14, and up to 20% of adolescents experience a mental disorder each year, although it remains largely unrecognized and untreated. Adolescent mental health issues are predictive for a number of high-risk behaviors, such as self-harm, drug abuse, risky sexual behavior, violence, etc. These behaviors have long-lasting consequences that affect adolescents throughout their lives (Kessler et al., 2009; Patel et al., 2008). Bearing in mind that suicide is one of the main reasons for adolescent mortality, the topic of mental health seems very important to both - scientists and practitioners in the field of mental health intervention and promotion.

In Serbia, 10.8% of adolescents report having a “bad” mood, and 21.9% report feeling anxious at least once a week. According to UNICEF⁴, just 18% of adolescents in Serbia seek help from mental health professionals, and that 30% of adolescents are unsure of where to look for psychological support. In addition, various events that occurred in Serbia earlier in the past years, such as the lockdown during the COVID-19 (Nguyen et al., 2022), and the mass shooting at the Vladislav Ribnikar primary school (Pejuskovic, Lecic-Tosevski, 2023), had certainly compromised the mental health of Serbian adolescents. Still, there is no clear research results that can reliably indicate the prevalence of symptoms of compromised mental health after these events.

Adolescence is a sensitive developmental period which can be marked by different types of discomfort such as unpleasant emotions (e.g., anxiety) at home or at school (Crandon et al., 2022; Franić et al., 2010; Milovanović, 2020), or exposure to different types of peer violence (e.g., Busch et al., 2015; Dinić et al., 2016). Bearing in mind these research results, mentioned events in Serbia, the nature of prevention provided by health and other institutions, as well as contemporary expert tendencies to emphasize positive indicators of mental health (such as life satisfaction and functional emotion regulation), this topic deserves greater research and

³ <https://www.who.int/data/>

⁴ <https://www.unicef.org/serbia/en/mental-health-and-well-being>

public attention, but also greater attention of counselors who deal with the mental health of adolescents. The additional need arises from the lack of research on this topic specifically on the adolescent population in Serbia

2. Life Satisfaction and Emotion Regulation as Mental Health Indicators – Definitions and Relations

Increasing number of research suggest that positive indicators should be prioritized above the absence of psychopathological symptoms in defining mental health. According to Diener (1984), there are three components of subjective well-being: a high level of positive affect, a low level of negative affect, and life satisfaction. The majority of experts agree that life satisfaction is recognized as an essential element of mental health. Satisfaction with life is a cognitive aspect of subjective wellbeing that relates to an individual’s assessment of the value of their own life path (Diener et al., 1999), and although it is partially genetic influences, it is also influenced by environmental circumstances (Sadiković et al., 2018). According to the findings of earlier research, having a high level of happiness and life satisfaction is highly and positive correlated with mental health (Lombardo et al., 2018; Marquez et al., 2023), especially in adolescence (Freire, Ferreira, 2020; Von Soest et al., 2020).

Adolescence is also considered a crucial developmental period for managing emotions, as indicated by the results of numerous studies (Schweizer et al., 2023; Silvers, 2022). Compared to adults and children, adolescents have higher levels of emotional fluctuation, bad mood, and heightened sensitivity to pleasant and fulfilling experiences (Riediger et al., 2011; Spear, 2011), and non-adaptive emotional regulation has been prospectively associated with poor mental health in adolescence (e.g., McLaughlin et al., 2011). Emotion regulation is a crucial component of emotional processes that mediates between many prerequisites for reporting feelings and the actual emotional reaction (Gross, John, 2003). This kind of regulation starts either from an externally triggered activating event or from an individual’s evaluation of a mental representation, independent of the externally triggered event. Evaluation of the event or the mental representation further sets off a chain reaction of behavioral and physiological

symptoms that can be controlled prior to the actual expression of an emotion. Authors differentiate two fundamentally distinct forms of emotional regulation: emotional suppression and cognitive reappraisal (Gross, John, 2003). Emotional suppression is the process of controlling one’s own emotional reaction to prevent its expression, whereas cognitive reappraisal is a process of reinterpreting a triggering event that modifies the emotional response in an appropriate way (Gross, 1988).

Numerous researches have examined the relationship between emotion regulation and life satisfaction on different levels – from genetic (e.g., Milovanović, Sadiković, Kodžopeljić, 2018) to phenotypic (e.g., Chervovsky, Hunt, 2019). The majority of these studies have found that life satisfaction has negative relationships with emotional suppression and positive relationships with cognitive reappraisal (Perrone-McGovern et al., 2015; Randal et al., 2014; Yiğit et al., 2014). Hu, Zhang, and Wang (2015) in their meta-analysis study support these results, although other research indicates that these effects may not exist (Liliana, Nicoleta, 2014). A number of study findings (e.g., Richards, Gross, 2000; Srivastava et al., 2009) suggest that emotional suppression is mostly dysfunctional type of emotion regulation strategies. Emotion suppression results in reduced memory function, a rise in insufficient physiological reaction, and a decline in the quality of interpersonal connections. Adolescents who often use emotional suppression are likely to experience poor mental health and reduced social functioning (Chervovsky, Hunt, 2019; Schäfer et al., 2017; Verzeletti et al., 2016). On the other hand, cognitive control was linked to higher cognitive reappraisal tendencies throughout adolescence (Lantrip et al., 2016) which frequently produces better mental health through stress reduction, adequate fear management, and higher general resilience (Kuhlman et al., 2021; Shapero et al., 2019; Willner et al., 2022).

3. Current Study

Recently, a lot of attention has been paid to adolescents and children in Serbia, mostly in the context of school mental health, but also their status in civil and criminal proceedings (Bačićanin, Hubić Nurković, 2022; Ćorić, 2019; Kostić, 2022; Obradović, 2019). Bearing in mind the recent events in Serbia, it seems that the mental health of adolescents is one of the

significant phenomena that deserves additional attention. If the dimension of the philosophical-legal discussion regarding the right to happiness (Ćorić, 2022) is included, this problem can be seen as multi-layered. From a psychological point of view, mental health should also be studied at the level of individual differences in some personal traits such as subjective well-being and emotional regulation, especially since scientific works dealing with adolescents in Serbia on this topic are very rare. If we add to all this the gender differences in the expression of emotions as well as the decreasing trend of satisfaction with life in adolescence (e.g., Gross, John, 2003; Rogier, Garofalo, Velotti, 2019), this topic is gaining importance both in the scientific and in the practical field.

The main aim of this research is to examine the relations between life satisfaction and two dimensions of emotion regulation in the sample of adolescents. We assume that cognitive reappraisal will positively, and emotional suppression negatively contribute to the level of life satisfaction in adolescence. Additionally, the relationships of the mentioned variables with the socio-demographic characteristics of the sample, such as gender and age, will also be examined.

4. Method

4.1 Sample and Procedure

The sample consisted of 155 adolescents (45% males) from Serbia. The average age of participants was 13.44 years ($SD = 1.65$). The examination took place through an online platform that was developed as part of the project activities. Adolescents received a link to their parents' e-mails with a unique code, after which they could access the platform and answer the questions from the questionnaire completely anonymously, after giving consent from their parents and themselves. The research was approved by the ethics committee of the author's institution (submission ID: 202010291658_SyRk). The GENIUS project activities were based on the previous cycle of projects (see Smederevac et al., 2019) in which authors had already made a significant contribution to understanding the mental health of young people. The research took place in the period 2021-2023.

4.2. Instruments

In the research, two instruments were used to measure certain indicators of the mental health of youth:

4.2.1. Satisfaction With Life Scale (SWLS: Diener et al., 1985). This one-dimensional rating scale consists of 5 items (e.g., 2. *Everything in my life is great.*), with 7-point Likert response type (from 1 - *not at all true for me* to 7 - *completely true for me*). We used 5-point form of SWLS in accordance to previous research with children and adolescents (e.g., Bendayan et al., 2013).

4.2.2 Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ: Gross, John, 2003). ERQ contains 10 items that measure two strategies: cognitive reappraisal - CR (6 items; e.g., *When I want to feel happier, I think about something different.*) and emotional suppression - ES (4 items; e.g., *I keep my feelings to myself.*) through seven-point Likert-type answering scale (from 1 - *strongly disagree* to 7 - *strongly agree*). We used 5-point form of ERQ in accordance to previous research with children and adolescents (e.g., Gong et al., 2021).

5. Results

Descriptive parameters are shown in Table 1. All variables are normally distributed, according to the Tabachnick and Fidell (2016) criteria: $-1.00 < Sk$ and $Ku < 1.00$. The reliability (α) of the used measures is also at a satisfactory level ($>.70$).

Table 1: *Descriptive statistics for SWLS and ERQ*

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Sk</i>	<i>Ku</i>	α
SWLS	20.14	4.24	-0.83	0.33	.87
Cognitive Reappraisal	21.54	4.60	-0.05	-0.26	.80
Emotional Suppression	10.87	3.91	-0.04	-0.62	.78

Note. *M* – mean; *SD* – standard deviation, *Sk* – skewnees; *Ku* – kutrosis; α – reliability.

Correlations between measures are low, but mostly significant. SWLS achieves a positive correlation with cognitive reappraisal ($r = .16$, p

<.05), and negative with emotional suppression ($r = -.25, p < .01$). Two ERQ measures are not significantly correlated ($r = .07, p = .34$). Age is positive correlated with emotional suppression ($r = .23, p < .01$), but negative with SWLS ($r = -.17, p < .05$), and cognitive reappraisal ($r = -.22, p < .01$). Gender differences are detected only on the dimension of emotional suppression in favor of males ($t = 3.09, p < .01$).

5.2. Regression analysis

By looking at the results of multiple regression analysis, it is concluded that the regression model is significant. ERQ dimensions explain 10% of the variance in life satisfaction among adolescents (Table 2).

Table 2: *Emotion regulation and satisfaction with life: Regression analysis*

$F = 8.24, p < .01, R = .31; R^2 = .10$	β	t	p
Cognitive Reappraisal	.19	2.40	.01
Emotional Suppression	-.27	-3.45	.00

Multiple regression analysis suggested that both ERQ dimensions are significant predictors of life satisfaction among adolescents. Cognitive reappraisal has positive, and emotional suppression negative contribution to life satisfaction in this developmental period. Thus, life satisfaction, as one measure of mental health, appears to be much higher among adolescents who are less likely to conceal emotions and who are more adept at reframing stressful events.

6. Discussion

The main aim of this research was to examine the contribution of emotion regulation to the life satisfaction level in Serbian adolescents. We assumed that in adolescence, emotional suppression will have a negative contribution on life satisfaction and cognitive reappraisal a favorable one. Furthermore, we also wanted to examine the associations between the aforementioned variables and the socio-demographic attributes of the sample (age and gender).

We got the result that male adolescents are more prone to suppress their emotions in comparison to female adolescents. The explanation of

this result could be fined in the proces of socialization. While male gender socialization would have caused males to suppress their emotions, women may have been taught to intentionally pay attention to their feelings (Gross and John, 1998). Indeed, most research suggest that male replace unpleasant emotion reactions with the expression of anger through violent and aggressive behavior (Gratz et al. 2009). Moreover, long-term suppression of emotions can therefore also lead to excessive situations, where anger is expressed uncontrollably and to the detriment of others (Rogier, Garofalo, Velotti, 2019). Therefore, it seems that psychological treatments aimed at emotion management are of key importance in the period of adolescence for boys. There is also a decreasing trend of life satisfaction and cognitive reappraisal, and a growing trend of emotional suppression with age. Adolescence is a sensitive developmental period which can be marked by different types of discomfort, and emotional variation, even on a daily basis (Larson, Lampman-Petratis, 1989; Reitsema et al., 2022). It is possible that over time, adolescents suppress emotional variations more often than reframing them, which over time reduces resources for dealing with stressful life circumstances and compromises life satisfaction. For these reasons, with the first physiological changes in adolescents, it is necessary to approach them with caution and counseling in the context of emotional reactions and coping with emotions, which is especially important for parents, teachers, and mental health practitioners.

Our hypothesis that cognitive reappraisal will positively contribute to the level of life satisfaction in adolescence was confirmed. Adolescents who more use the strategy of cognitive reappraisal when dealing with stressful circumstances, are also more satisfied with their life. Positive associations between the reappraisal strategy and measures of positive psychological functioning are very common in psychological literature (e.g., Gross, John, 2003). That research suggested that reappraisal strategy reduces every-day negative sentiments, and also raise positive sentiments and adaptive behaviors. Bearing in mind that the evaluation of one’s own life implies an insight into everyday life, this finding is not surprising. Reinterpreting negative emotions and stressful events appears to significantly improve well-being, through improving intrapersonal and social functioning in adolescence (e.g., Balzarotti, John, Gross, 2010; Gross, John, 2003),

which essentially constitute the main domain of adolescent life. Our assumption about negative associations of suppression strategy with life satisfaction in adolescence were also confirmed. This result is also very common in previous studies (e.g., Gross, John, 2003), and it can be explained through the process model of emotion regulation (Gross, 2001). According to this model, the use of suppression strategy, which is a response-focused strategy, inhibits the emotional reaction instead of altering it. If it takes place on a daily basis, emotional suppression can significantly compromise daily functioning, and in the long term, mental health, as well as life satisfaction. That is why the adolescent period is very important in the context of mental health promotion, as well as primary and secondary prevention of behavioral disorders. Therefore, our research demonstrates that although emotional suppression has a more prominent and discriminating influence on wellbeing than cognitive reappraisal, which has more extensive repercussions, control through reappraisal strategy is more adaptive than emotional suppression strategy in terms of life satisfaction in adolescence.

6.1. Limitations, future directions and practical implications

This study has several limitations. First of all, it seems that a larger sample, which includes not only adolescents, but also children, would be more suitable for examining the relationship between emotional regulation and life satisfaction. This is primarily related to monitoring the socio-emotional development of an individual, which should be started in the earlier stages of development, and not exclusively in adolescence, although adolescence is an emotionally turbulent period. Therefore, a longitudinal study could more clearly provide conclusions about the specific development of emotional regulation and life satisfaction, but also data about specific influences, and not exclusively relationships, as is the case in this study. On the other hand, self-reports were used as the main source of assessment in this study. Given the socially desirable response, which is often a flaw in psychological research, it seems that in subsequent attempts, the mentioned constructs should be examined in an experimental way, or in a way of more objective assessment, e.g., by others or through some semi-standardized interview or checklist.

Finally, it is necessary to mention the practical implications of this study. This study primarily aims to indicate the trend of the relationship

between emotional regulation and life satisfaction in adolescents with typical development. In healthcare institutions, most of the attention is given to adolescents who have certain psychosocial difficulties and emotional problems. On this place, we are talking about secondary and tertiary prevention carried out by institutions responsible for the mental health of the population. Nevertheless, our study indicates that even in adolescents with typical development who do not have psychosocial difficulties, a relatively complicated situation of emotional management of turbulent changes occurs, which can significantly threaten the life satisfaction, especially in boys, which intensifies with age. Therefore, it seems that institutions that work with adolescents, primarily schools, must be equipped with significant human resources that can contribute to realizing the right of adolescents to functional emotional development in this period and mental health. The relatively worrying prevalence of various mental states among adolescents from the beginning of this paper, suggests that significant improvements are needed in psychological and pedagogical work with adolescents, above all transparent work of these services within school institutions and centers that could contribute to a higher percentage of adolescents who appear mental health worker in situations where there are certain emotional problems or dissatisfaction with the current life satisfaction. Additional investments in the development of human resources that would deal with the mental health of young people within the institutions, would contribute significantly to young people exercising their right to mental health in.

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